

A Meteorological Data Journal

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Overlay Journal Infrastructure for Meteorological Sciences (OJIMS)

The OJIMS project is investigating the idea of data publication in the atmospheric sciences. It is creating the required mechanics for overlay journals and examine their long term sustainability. The project also set up a document repository for the atmospheric sciences. This would preserve a range of documents relevant to atmospheric science including journal papers, technical reports, and images.

The project partners are the Royal Meteorological Society and The National Centre for Atmospheric Science (NCAS). The OJIMS project is funded by NERC and JISC

<http://proj.badc.rl.ac.uk/ojims>

Do people want a data journal?

This poster describes the results of a survey of scientists conducted by the Royal Meteorological Society to assess users' views of the creation and operation of the proposed Journal of Meteorological Data. It also describes reactions to supervised run-throughs of a demo of the Journal of Meteorological Data. The survey and demo were conducted at the NCAS Conference in Bristol on 8-10 December 2008.

The concept behind the Journal of Meteorological Data is to extend the scientific discipline of peer review to data. It received a strong positive response in the survey with 69% agreed that they would like to access data from an RMetS Journal. 67% agreed that they were more likely to deposit their data in a data centre if they could obtain academic credit through a data journal. Almost all respondents were users or creators of meteorological data of some kind. The only existing data journal in this area is aimed at all environmental sciences and 91% of respondents had never heard of it. Atmospheric Science Letters, the RMetS on-line journal, was the best known on-line meteorological journal with 93% having heard of it.

Pie chart showing people like the idea of data journal

Can you make a data journal a reality?

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Screen shots of demo

A demonstration of a Journal of Meteorological Data (the demo) was created and run by Sam Pepler, BADC. The demo was based on the open source software OJS. It allowed volunteers to approach the idea of the new journal as a reader, an author or a reviewer. It addressed issues including: licensing data, page charges and article content. Volunteers were supervised by a guide from the OJIMS team. See screen shot below.

Review process?

RMetS is actively considering it